

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE IMPORTANCE OF MEDIA IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of information and media in the context of globalization and its impact on national mentality. Threats of the media world are based on its place in the global world, the essence of the acceleration of globalization.

Keywords: Information and media, cultural exchange, information dissemination, bridging boundaries, influence and persuasion, global awareness, social connectivity, globalization, national mentality, content, virtualization.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СМИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ АБСТРАКТНЫЙ

В данной статье подчеркивается важность информации и средств массовой информации в условиях глобализации и ее влияние на национальный менталитет. Угрозы медиамира основаны на его месте в глобальном мире, сути ускорения глобализации.

Ключевые слова: информация и средства массовой информации, культурный обмен, распространение информации, преодоление границ, влияние и убеждение, глобальная осведомленность, социальная связь, глобализация, национальный менталитет, контент, виртуализация.

In today's global and informational world, the importance of media is increasing day by day. The importance of information technology is increasing in every aspect of society's life. Especially in the conditions of globalization, it was shown that the influence of the media world is strong. The increasing virtualization of human life, significant use of media in science serve to further increase its importance. Mahatma Gandhi, the Indian national hero, said: "I cannot close the doors and windows of my house because fresh air must come in, but dust, rain, and storms can also come in with the air and turn my house upside down." I can't let go"

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This thought of Gandhi was given directly to the process of globalization, and at the beginning of the 20th century, the processes of globalization began to worry scientists¹. Globalization is a worldwide process of economic, political, cultural and religious integration and unification². The word globalization is derived from the word globe, which means spherification, rounding.

Globalization refers to the process of increasing interconnectedness and interdependence between countries, societies and people around the world. It involves the global exchange of goods, services, ideas and cultures and is driven by advances in technology, communication and trade. Globalization has led to the integration of economies, the flow of capital and investment across borders, the spread of information and technology, and the interconnection of cultures and societies. While globalization has facilitated economic growth and development, it has also raised concerns about inequality, cultural homogeneity, environmental degradation, and the erosion of national sovereignty³.

Media plays a crucial role in the context of globalization as it facilitates the flow of information, ideas, and cultural exchange across borders. Here are some key reasons highlighting the importance of media in the context of globalization:

1. Information dissemination: Media, including news outlets, social media, television, and online platforms, play a key role in disseminating information globally. This allows people to stay informed about global events, trends, and developments in real-time⁴.

2. Cultural exchange: Global media platforms enable the sharing of cultural products such as music, films, literature, and fashion, which helps in promoting cultural diversity and awareness across the world.

3. Bridging boundaries: Media acts as a bridge between different cultures, languages, and societies, facilitating communication and understanding between people from diverse backgrounds.

4. Influence and persuasion: Media has the power to shape public opinion, influence behaviors, and persuade individuals to adopt certain beliefs or values. This influence can transcend national borders and have a global impact.

¹ М. К. Gandhi. An Autobiography Or The Story of My Experiments With Truth. Dehli-1947. p 68

² Л. Е. Гринин. ВЕК ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. Москва-2008. с 47

³ Thomas L. Friedman "The Lexus and the Olive Tree: Understanding Globalization" 2022 y. 234 p

⁴ Arnold S. de Beer. Global Journalism Topical Issues and Media Systems. Stellenbosch University, South Africa. 2009 y. p 17

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5. Global awareness: Through media coverage and reporting, people are made aware of global issues such as climate change, human rights violations, and socio-political conflicts, prompting global discussions and actions.

6. Economic impact: Media plays a significant role in shaping consumer preferences and promoting global brands and products, thereby contributing to the global economy and trade.

7. Social connectivity: Social media platforms have revolutionized the way people connect and communicate globally, breaking down barriers and enabling instantaneous interactions between individuals from different parts of the world.

In conclusion, media is a powerful tool in the context of globalization, enabling the exchange of information, ideas, and culture on a global scale. Its role in shaping perceptions, influencing behaviors, and fostering global awareness makes it a vital component in the interconnected world of today.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Arnold S. de Beer. Global Journalism Topical Issues and Media Systems. Stellenbosch University, South Africa. 2009 y.
2. Curran, J. (2002). Media and Power. London and New York: Routledge. p.179.
3. Thomas L. Friedman "The Lexus and the Olive Tree: Understanding Globalization" 2022 y. 234 p
4. Thomas L. Friedman "The Lexus and the Olive Tree: Understanding Globalization" 2022 y. 234 p
5. Л. Е. Гринин. ВЕК ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. Москва-2008. с 47